

Challenges in Process Mining

Thank you for considering participating in this survey!

Aim of this survey:

- In a previous study, we discovered a number of challenges that have been reported by process mining analysts
- In this work, we want to learn more about these challenges, if you experienced them already during a project and especially if and how you managed to overcome them.

Please note

- To participate in this survey, you need to have been involved in at least one process mining project. If this does not apply to you, you are welcome to end the survey at this point, we would still like to thank you very much for your willingness to participate!
- The survey will take you approx. 30-60 min. The time investment depends on the experience you have and the number of challenges you can comment on.
- You will have the option to pause the survey and come back to the questionnaire in case you need a break or have any time restrictions.
- Your participation in this survey is completely anonymous! The data you will share will only be used in the context of academic research with the aim to be published.
- At the end of this survey, you will have the option to leave your e-mail address (which can't be linked to your replies) to receive updates and information regarding the ProMISE project (see below) and relevant publications. Via this medium, we will also share the results of this survey with all the participants interested.

If you have any further questions or comments, please contact: lisa.zimmermann@unisg.ch

Note: We conduct this survey as part of the academic research project "ProMISE: Process Mining Support for End Users" (funded by the [Swiss National Science Foundation](#), Grant no: 200021 197032) in which we aim to deepen the existing understanding of how process mining is conducted by analysts in practice.

Please answer the following questions:

1. In which country do you currently live?

[Please choose] ▼

2. What industry do you work in?

[Please choose] ▼

3. What is your job title? You can put '-' if you prefer not to answer this question.

4. In how many processes mining projects have you been involved?

You should have had an active role in the projects you count. Did you actively worked on the process analysis with a process mining tool or engaged in the definition of the project scope, the data collection or data pre-processing phase?

- 0
- 1-2
- 3-5
- 6-10
- >10

5. How many years of experience to you have in the field of processes mining?

- <1
- 1-2
- 3-5
- 6-10
- >10

6. How do you rate your level of expertise in process mining?

- Novice
- Basic
- Average
- Good
- Advanced

7. How do you rate your level of expertise in analyzing processes with process mining?

- Novice
- Basic
- Average
- Good
- Advanced

8. Have you actively worked on any of the following phases of a process mining project?

Please select all that apply.

- Question Formulation (Phase in which the research question and the goal of the project is defined)
- Data Collection (Phase in which relevant data is extracted from one or more source systems)
- Data Preparation (Phase in which the data is transformed into a process mining conformant event log, which might include attributes or additional tables that form a data model)
- Mining & Analysis (Phase in which one or several process mining algorithms are applied to derive insights from the process)
- Stakeholder Evaluation (Phase in which the results of the previous phase are presented and discussed with the Stakeholders)
- Implementation (The implementation of process insights to manipulate the real-world execution of the process)
- None of the above

question('D007')

You indicated that you have been involved in many process mining project phases. This means that you may have also encountered many challenges during these phases and can provide valuable insights into them.

However, since we estimate a **total time effort of more than 1.5 hours** for completing the questionnaire considering all challenges, **feel free to select those challenges from the list below, that you can relate to and on which you can provide some information during this questionnaire.**

In the remainder of the questionnaire, you will only be asked about these challenges.

Please select at least 5.

question('D008')

Which of these challenges can you relate to and on which can you provide additional information from your experience?

	Yes, I will comment.	No, I won't comment.	I can't relate.	I don't understand.
1. Question Formulation: It is hard to find a question that is not too precise (might limit the analyst in the exploration of the data) and not too broad (might prevent the analyst from identifying meaningful insights).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Access and Use of Process Mining Tools: Process mining tools might be unavailable, inconvenient to use, or a governance is missing to structure the tool usage in the organization.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Process Mining Suitability: It can be difficult to select process mining as a suitable method for the task/goal/question at hand.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Data Extraction: Problems can occur during the retrieval (i.e., identification and extraction) of event data from any kind of source.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Data Availability: Event data is not always available as it might not be stored in the source system, or it is missing because process steps are conducted outside of the system.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Data Access: Permissions (legal, regulatory, organizational) or means to access the data are missing.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. Source System & Data Structure Knowledge: Information and documentation of the source system and its database structure might not be available.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. Data Transformation: It can be problematic to prepare a process mining compliant event log based on raw event data.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
9. Data Quality: It can be problematic to deal with data of low quality either in the final event log or already in the raw data.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
10. Data Validation: It can be difficult to check the data accuracy or the suitability of the available data to be analyzed with the help of process mining.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
11. Tool Knowledge: The analyst is not familiar with the tool, lacks knowledge on how to use specific functions of the tool or hasn't used the tool in a while.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

12. Event Log & Data Model Understanding: Data models or event logs can come in different formats and with different levels of complexity and elements.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
13. Process Mining Techniques: Process mining tools are missing (or insufficiently support) certain process mining functionalities.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
14. Access to Additional Information: Permissions to access the process documentations or the option to collaborate with knowledgeable stakeholders (e.g., process owner) are missing, or such information regarding the specific process simply do not exist.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
15. Process Visualization: The interpretation of the visualization of a process in form of a directly-follows-graph (DFG) (as used in many process mining tools) is challenging as they are not able to deal with concurrency and should be cautiously read when filtered.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
16. Analysis Experience: It can be problematic to conduct an analysis if the analyst doesn't have a lot of experience but at the same time, gaining the experience and finding project partners with the required experience and skillset is challenging.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
17. Analysis Focus: It can be problematic to maintain the big picture of the analysis despite the available details.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
18. Conclusions & Question Answering: It is not trivial to draw conclusions based on the results of the process discovery.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
19. Recommendations & Next steps: Formulating a concrete recommendation or deriving concrete next steps to foster the process improvement is not always straightforward based on the analysis insights.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
20. Process Domain Understanding: The analysts might not be familiar with the domain & domain-specific terminology that is used in the event and attribute descriptions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
21. Collaboration with Stakeholders: There can be misunderstandings due to mismatching expectations, different process perspectives and different backgrounds of the stakeholders and the analysts.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
22. Business Process Complexity: Business processes are oftentimes complex in nature and therefore hard to analyze with process mining, due to their inherent complexity and dependencies among them.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

23. Enablement / Training: On the one hand, there may be a lack of available training opportunities, or it is not easy to find an optimal training course, and on the other hand, designing training courses is difficult because knowledge from different areas is required to be successful in process mining.

question('QF04')

Challenge: Question Formulation

Phase: Research Question

Description: The **formulation of a proper question for the process mining project is challenging**, as it is hard to find a question that is **not too precise** (might limit the analyst in the exploration of the data) and **not too broad** (might prevent the analyst from identifying meaningful insights).

Exemplary Statement:

- "I think the analysis should always follow the question. So, I would base my steps on the question, but at the same time, it is often hard to identify the correct question."

question('QF07')

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
- No

question('QF09')

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question('QF04')

Challenge: Question Formulation

Phase: Research Question

Description: The **formulation of a proper question for the process mining project is challenging**, as it is hard to find a question that is **not too precise** (might limit the analyst in the exploration of the data) and **not too broad** (might prevent the analyst from identifying meaningful insights).

Exemplary Statement:

- "I think the analysis should always follow the question. So, I would base my steps on the question, but at the same time, it is often hard to identify the correct question."

question('QF02')

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

question('QF03')

Mitigation Approach

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

question('QF05')

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

question('QF10')

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("UT04")

Challenge: Access and Use of Process Mining Tools

Phase: Research Question

Description: The access to process mining tools or the choice of which tool to use is **challenging**, as process mining tools **might be unavailable, inconvenient to use, or a governance is missing** to structure the tool usage in the organization.

Exemplary Statement:

- "I think the biggest challenge is that most companies do not have the tools implemented."

question("UT09")

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
- No

question("UT07")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question("UT04")

Challenge: Access and Use of Process Mining Tools

Phase: Research Question

Description: The access to process mining tools or the choice of which tool to use is **challenging**, as process mining tools **might be unavailable, inconvenient to use, or a governance is missing** to structure the tool usage in the organization.

Exemplary Statement:

- "I think the biggest challenge is that most companies do not have the tools implemented."

question("UT02")

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

question("UT03")

Mitigation

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

question("UT05")

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

question("UT08")

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("MS04")

Challenge: Process Mining Suitability

Phase: Research Question

Description: The **identification of process mining as a suitable method for the problem or goal at hand is challenging**.

Exemplary Statement:

- "I think it makes a lot of sense to use process mining methods. But at the same time, you don't need process mining to answer a lot of the questions. You can use process mining as a tool in the toolbox where you have a lot of other tools that you use around."

question("MS08")

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
- No

question("MS07")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question("MS04")

Challenge: Process Mining Suitability

Phase: Research Question

Description: The identification of process mining as a suitable method for the problem or goal at hand is challenging.

Exemplary Statement:

- "I think it makes a lot of sense to use process mining methods. But at the same time, you don't need process mining to answer a lot of the questions. You can use process mining as a tool in the toolbox where you have a lot of other tools that you use around."

question("MS02")

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

question("MS03")

Mitigation

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods /mitigation strategies /measures did you use?

question("MS05")

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

question("MS06")

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("DE04")

Challenge: Data Extraction

Phase: Data Collection

Description: The extraction of data is challenging, as problems can occur during the retrieval (i.e., identification and extraction) of event data from any kind of source.

Exemplary Statement:

- "I think gathering the data is a technical challenge and there's not much to elaborate there. You quite often need to extract data from information systems that are not thought for being able to export clean logs."

question("DE06")

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
 No

question("DE07")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
 No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
 No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question("DE04")

Challenge: Data Extraction

Phase: Data Collection

Description: The extraction of data is challenging, as problems can occur during the retrieval (i.e., identification and extraction) of event data from any kind of source.

Exemplary Statement:

- "I think gathering the data is a technical challenge and there's not much to elaborate there. You quite often need to extract data from information systems that are not thought for being able to export clean logs."

question("DE02")

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

Mitigation

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods /mitigation strategies /measures did you use?

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

Challenge: Data Availability

Phase: Data Collection

Description: **Having the required event data available is challenging, as data might not be stored in the source system, or it is missing because process steps are conducted outside of the system.**

Exemplary Statement:

- "In one of the projects, we did not have enough event data because the process was recently changed. And we didn't have enough cases so we couldn't continue with the project."

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
- No

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

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Phase: Data Collection

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Exemplary Statement:

- "In one of the projects, we did not have enough event data because the process was recently changed. And we didn't have enough cases so we couldn't continue with the project."

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

Mitigation

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods /mitigation strategies /measures did you use?

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("DX04")

Challenge: Data Access

Phase: Data Collection

Description: Getting access to the data is challenging, as permissions (legal, regulatory, organizational) or means to access the data can be missing.

Exemplary Statement:

- "Another challenge is also to check if we can get the data. Because we also already had cases where we couldn't get the data, it was not accessible, not for me and not for the data scientists."

question("DX06")

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
- No

question("DX07")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question("DX04")

Challenge: Data Access

Phase: Data Collection

Description: Getting access to the data is challenging, as permissions (legal, regulatory, organizational) or means to access the data can be missing.

Exemplary Statement:

- "Another challenge is also to check if we can get the data. Because we also already had cases where we couldn't get the data, it was not accessible, not for me and not for the data scientists."

question("DX02")

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

question("DX03")

Mitigation

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods /mitigation strategies /measures did you use?

question("DX05")

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

question("DX08")

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("SK04")

Challenge: Source System & Data Structure Knowledge

Phase: Data Collection

Description: To gain knowledge regarding the source system and the data structure within the source system is challenging, as information and documentation of the same might not be available.

Exemplary Statement:

- "Most systems require knowledge, and I don't have that because I'm not an expert on the system and the settings there."

question("SK06")

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
- No

question("SK07")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question("SK04")

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Phase: Data Collection

Description: To gain knowledge regarding the source system and the data structure within the source system is challenging, as information and documentation of the same might not be available.

Exemplary Statement:

- "Most systems require knowledge, and I don't have that because I'm not an expert on the system and the settings there."

question("SK02")

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

question("SK03")

Mitigation

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods /mitigation strategies /measures did you use?

question("SK05")

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

question("SK08")

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("DT04")

Challenge: Data Transformation

Phase: Data Preprocessing

Description: The transformation of the data extracted from the source system into the event log format is challenging, as it can be problematic to prepare a process mining compliant event log based on raw event data. It specifically covers adding attributes or activities to the event log and finding the correct level of aggregation depending on the case key.

Exemplary Statement:

- "I think the biggest challenge is getting your data in a format that is ready to analyze. So typically, data comes from ERP systems like SAP or something like that. And it's not straightforward to transform it into an event log or a XES format."

question("DT06")

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
 No

question("DT07")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
 No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
 No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question("DT04")

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Exemplary Statement:

- "I think the biggest challenge is getting your data in a format that is ready to analyze. So typically, data comes from ERP systems like SAP or something like that. And it's not straightforward to transform it into an event log or a XES format."

question("DT02")

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

Mitigation

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods /mitigation strategies /measures did you use?

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extend did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

Challenge: Data Quality

Phase: Data Preprocessing

Description: It is challenging if the **quality of the data extracted from the source system does not meet the quality expectations**, as it can be problematic to **deal with data of low quality** either in the final event log or already in the raw data.

Exemplary Statement:

- *"The most problematic challenges are data quality issues. Frequent data quality issues also the mismatch of data recording and the business level reasoning."*

Do you understand the challenge?

Yes

No

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

Challenge: Data Quality

Phase: Data Preprocessing

Description: It is challenging if the **quality of the data extracted from the source system does not meet the quality expectations**, as it can be problematic to **deal with data of low quality** either in the final event log or already in the raw data.

Exemplary Statement:

- *"The most problematic challenges are data quality issues. Frequent data quality issues also the mismatch of data recording and the business level reasoning."*

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

Uncritical Critical

Infrequent Frequent

No Blocker Project Blocker

Mitigation

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods /mitigation strategies /measures did you use?

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extend did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("DV04")

Challenge: Data Validation

Phase: Data Preprocessing

Description: The validation of the data, (i.e. the check of correctness & completeness of the data) is challenging. It can be difficult to validate the data and the suitability of the available data to be analyzed with the help of process mining.

Exemplary Statement:

- "My experience is that I need a lot of time to check if the data is ok and accurate."

question("DV06")

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
- No

question("DV07")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question("DV04")

Challenge: Data Validation

Phase: Data Preprocessing

Description: The validation of the data, (i.e. the check of correctness & completeness of the data) is challenging. It can be difficult to validate the data and the suitability of the available data to be analyzed with the help of process mining.

Exemplary Statement:

- "My experience is that I need a lot of time to check if the data is ok and accurate."

question("DV02")

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

question("DV03")

Mitigation

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

question("DV05")

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

question("DV08")

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("TK04")

Challenge: Tool Knowledge

Phase: Mining & Analysis

Description: Having proper knowledge of how to use the process mining tool for a specific analysis task is challenging. Specifically, it can be problematic for the analyst to conduct the analysis if she is not familiar with the tool, lacks knowledge on how to use specific functions of the tool or hasn't used the tool in a while.

Exemplary Statement:

- "The tools work all in a very similar way and they basically use the same algorithms. But remembering where those patterns are and how to click in the right sequence, it's not always easy."

question("TK07")

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
- No

question("TK09")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question('TK04')

Challenge: Tool Knowledge

Phase: Mining & Analysis

Description: Having proper knowledge of how to use the process mining tool for a specific analysis task is challenging. Specifically, it can be problematic for the analyst to conduct the analysis if she is not familiar with the tool, lacks knowledge on how to use specific functions of the tool or hasn't used the tool in a while.

Exemplary Statement:

- "The tools work all in a very similar way and they basically use the same algorithms. But remembering where those patterns are and how to click in the right sequence, it's not always easy."

question('TK02')

Please indicate your assessment.
For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

Uncritical	<input type="range"/>	Critical
Infrequent	<input type="range"/>	Frequent
No Blocker	<input type="range"/>	Project Blocker

question('TK03')

Mitigation Approach
You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.
What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

question('TK05')

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

To which extend did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

0% 100%

question('TK10')

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question('EU04')

Challenge: Event Log & Data Model Understanding

Phase: Mining & Analysis

Description: Understanding the event log or even the complete data model loaded for a process mining analysis is challenging, as data models or event logs can come in different formats and with different levels of complexity and elements. The challenge specifically occurs, when the format in a specific analysis differs from what the analyst is used to from other projects.

Exemplary Statements:

- "There are a lot of tools for the preprocessing, but there is no support for the understanding. Getting acquainted with the log is difficult."
- "Understanding the data model in the tool is probably the biggest challenge."

question('EU07')

Do you understand the challenge?

Yes

No

question('EU09')

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question("EU04")

Challenge: Event Log & Data Model Understanding

Phase: Mining & Analysis

Description: Understanding the event log or even the complete data model loaded for a process mining analysis is challenging, as data models or event logs can come in different formats and with different levels of complexity and elements. The challenge specifically occurs, when the format in a specific analysis differs from what the analyst is used to from other projects.

Exemplary Statements:

- "There are a lot of tools for the preprocessing, but there is no support for the understanding. Getting acquainted with the log is difficult."
- "Understanding the data model in the tool is probably the biggest challenge."

question("EU02")

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

question("EU03")

Mitigation Approach

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

question("EU05")

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extend did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

question("EU10")

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("TE04")

Challenge: Process Mining Techniques

Phase: Mining & Analysis

Description: Process mining tools are missing (or insufficiently support) certain process mining functionalities so that analysts are not able to solve certain problems during the analysis with the given tool or are not satisfied with the results of a technique.

Exemplary Statement:

- "I think solving this analysis problem is challenging, considering there is no methods for that in the tool."

question("TE07")

Do you understand the challenge?

Yes

No

question("TE09")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question("TE04")

Challenge: Process Mining Techniques

Phase: Mining & Analysis

Description: Process mining tools are missing (or insufficiently support) certain process mining functionalities so that analysts are not able to solve certain problems during the analysis with the given tool or are not satisfied with the results of a technique.

Exemplary Statement:

- "I think solving this analysis problem is challenging, considering there is no methods for that in the tool."

question("TE02")

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

question('TE03')

Mitigation Approach

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

question('TE05')

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

question('TE10')

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question('AI04')

Challenge: Access to Additional Information

Phase: Mining & Analysis

Description: If access to additional information is required during the analysis, it is challenging to retrieve this access. Permissions to access the process documentations or the option to collaborate with knowledgeable stakeholders (e.g., process owner) are missing, or such information regarding the specific process simply do not exist.

Exemplary Statements:

- "Sometimes process information are not documented, only the process owners or the domain experts can explain them."
- "If there is no access to additional information, I only retrieve what is already obvious from the process."

question('AI07')

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
 No

question('AI09')

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
 No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
 No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question('AI04')

Challenge: Access to Additional Information

Phase: Mining & Analysis

Description: If access to additional information is required during the analysis, it is challenging to retrieve this access. Permissions to access the process documentations or the option to collaborate with knowledgeable stakeholders (e.g., process owner) are missing, or such information regarding the specific process simply do not exist.

Exemplary Statements:

- "Sometimes process information are not documented, only the process owners or the domain experts can explain them."
- "If there is no access to additional information, I only retrieve what is already obvious from the process."

question('AI02')

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

Uncritical Critical

Infrequent Frequent

No Blocker Project Blocker

question('AI03')

Mitigation Approach

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

question('AI05')

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

question('AI10')

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("PV04")

Challenge: Process Visualization

Phase: Mining & Analysis

Description: The interpretation of the visualization of a process in form of a directly-follows-graph (DFG) (as used in many process mining tools) is challenging as they are not able to deal with concurrency and should be cautiously read when filtered.

Exemplary Statement:

- "There are many challenges in process mining. For example, the outcome of discovery algorithms can be imprecise in a way that they generate visualizations with lots of behavior that is not presented in the event logs. The notation used for visualizing process mining is not always accurate."

question("PV07")

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
- No

question("PV09")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question("PV03")

Mitigation Approach

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

question("PV05")

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

question("PV10")

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("PV04")

Challenge: Process Visualization

Phase: Mining & Analysis

Description: The interpretation of the visualization of a process in form of a directly-follows-graph (DFG) (as used in many process mining tools) is challenging as they are not able to deal with concurrency and should be cautiously read when filtered.

Exemplary Statement:

- "There are many challenges in process mining. For example, the outcome of discovery algorithms can be imprecise in a way that they generate visualizations with lots of behavior that is not presented in the event logs. The notation used for visualizing process mining is not always accurate."

question("PV02")

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

question("AE04")

Challenge: Analysis Experience

It is reported that **having enough experience to be able to successfully conduct a process mining analysis is perceived as challenging**. This challenge typically occurs during the fourth process mining project phase ("Mining & Analysis").

The "Analysis Experience" is found to be difficult, as it can be problematic if the analyst doesn't have a lot of experience. At the same time, gaining the experience and finding project partners with the required experience and skillset is challenging.

Exemplary Statement:

- "The analysts needs to be experienced in process mining, like with the correct mindset and understanding for the situation. It is a challenge if this person is not available."

question("AE07")

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
- No

question("AE09")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question('AE04')

Challenge: Analysis Experience

It is reported that **having enough experience to be able to successfully conduct a process mining analysis is perceived as challenging**. This challenge typically occurs during the fourth process mining project phase ("Mining & Analysis").

The "Analysis Experience" is found to be difficult, as it can be problematic if the analyst doesn't have a lot of experience. At the same time, gaining the experience and finding project partners with the required experience and skillset is challenging.

Exemplary Statement:

- *"The analysts needs to be experienced in process mining, like with the correct mindset and understanding for the situation. It is a challenge if this person is not available."*

question('AE02')

Please indicate your assessment.
For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

Uncritical	<input type="range"/>	Critical
Infrequent	<input type="range"/>	Frequent
No Blocker	<input type="range"/>	Project Blocker

question('AE03')

Mitigation Approach
You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.
What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

question('AE05')

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

0% 100%

question('AE10')

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question('AF04')

Challenge: Analysis Focus

Phase: Mining & Analysis

Description: **Keeping the focus on the research question during the analysis is challenging**. It can be problematic to maintain the big picture of the analysis despite the available details.

Exemplary Statement:

- *"It is really the biggest challenge to not lose yourself in the top-down analysis."*

question('AF07')

Do you understand the challenge?

Yes

No

question('AF09')

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question('AF04')

Challenge: Analysis Focus

Phase: Mining & Analysis

Description: **Keeping the focus on the research question during the analysis is challenging**. It can be problematic to maintain the big picture of the analysis despite the available details.

Exemplary Statement:

- *"It is really the biggest challenge to not lose yourself in the top-down analysis."*

question('AF02')

Please indicate your assessment.
For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

Uncritical	<input type="range"/>	Critical
Infrequent	<input type="range"/>	Frequent
No Blocker	<input type="range"/>	Project Blocker

Mitigation Approach

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

Challenge: Conclusions & Question Answering

Phase: Stakeholder Evaluation

Description: Answering the question and completing the analysis is challenging because it is not trivial to draw conclusions based on the results of the process discovery.

Exemplary Statement:

- "After analyzing for a while, I don't really know where to find the answers. I don't know what to answer to the given question. That is actually a common problem."

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
- No

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

Challenge: Conclusions & Question Answering

Phase: Stakeholder Evaluation

Description: Answering the question and completing the analysis is challenging because it is not trivial to draw conclusions based on the results of the process discovery.

Exemplary Statement:

- "After analyzing for a while, I don't really know where to find the answers. I don't know what to answer to the given question. That is actually a common problem."

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

Mitigation Approach

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("NS04")

Challenge: Recommendations & Next steps

Phase: Stakeholder Evaluation

Description: Giving recommendations and proposing next steps as a result of the process mining analysis is challenging, as formulating a concrete recommendation or deriving concrete next steps to foster the process improvement is not always straightforward based on the analysis insights.

Exemplary Statement:

- "The issue is really: What are you going to do with the results? What kind of recommendations or proposals to change the process can you really give based on it?"

question("NS07")

Do you understand the challenge?

Yes

No

question("NS09")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question("NS04")

Challenge: Recommendations & Next steps

Phase: Stakeholder Evaluation

Description: Giving recommendations and proposing next steps as a result of the process mining analysis is challenging, as formulating a concrete recommendation or deriving concrete next steps to foster the process improvement is not always straightforward based on the analysis insights.

Exemplary Statement:

- "The issue is really: What are you going to do with the results? What kind of recommendations or proposals to change the process can you really give based on it?"

question("NS02")

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

Uncritical Critical

Infrequent Frequent

No Blocker Project Blocker

question("NS03")

Mitigation Approach

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

question("NS05")

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

question("NS10")

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("DU04")

Challenge: Process Domain Understanding

Phase: Can potentially affect any project phase.

Description: It is **challenging to understand the process domain**. The analysts might **not be familiar with the domain & domain-specific terminology** that is used in the event and attribute descriptions.

Exemplary Statement:

- "I found it challenging, not understanding the background, the rules, the entire process - how it should work. I was confused by the domain specific terms and the activity names used."

question("DU07")

Do you understand the challenge?

Yes

No

question("DU09")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question("DU04")

Challenge: Process Domain Understanding

Phase: Can potentially affect any project phase.

Description: It is **challenging to understand the process domain**. The analysts might **not be familiar with the domain & domain-specific terminology** that is used in the event and attribute descriptions.

Exemplary Statement:

- "I found it challenging, not understanding the background, the rules, the entire process - how it should work. I was confused by the domain specific terms and the activity names used."

question("DU02")

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

question("DU03")

Mitigation Approach

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

question("DU05")

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

question("DU10")

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question("CS04")

Challenge: Collaboration with Stakeholders

Phase: Can potentially affect any project phase.

Description: The **collaboration with Stakeholders during the conduct of a process mining project is challenging**, as there can be **misunderstandings due to mismatching expectations, different process perspectives and different backgrounds** of the stakeholders and the analysts. The challenge also includes that fact that **stakeholders might be reluctant to participate in the success of a process mining project** in their organization.

Exemplary Statements:

- "It is difficult to understand the customer. To know what he wants and to make that translation from business to IT."
- "The challenge in the project was that I was hitting a wall with the Stakeholders. They didn't want that somebody external of their business puts his eyes on it."

question("CS07")

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
- No

question("CS09")

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
- No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question('CS04')

Challenge: Collaboration with Stakeholders

Phase: Can potentially affect any project phase.

Description: The **collaboration with Stakeholders during the conduct of a process mining project is challenging**, as there can be **misunderstandings due to mismatching expectations, different process perspectives and different backgrounds** of the stakeholders and the analysts. The challenge also includes that fact that **stakeholders might be reluctant to participate in the success of a process mining project** in their organization.

Exemplary Statements:

- "It is difficult to understand the customer. To know what he wants and to make that translation from business to IT."
- "The challenge in the project was that I was hitting a wall with the Stakeholders. They didn't want that somebody external of their business puts his eyes on it."

question('CS02')

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

question('CS03')

Mitigation Approach

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

question('CS05')

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

question('CS10')

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

question('PC04')

Challenge: Business Process Complexity

Phase: Can potentially affect any project phase.

Description: (Real-world) **business processes are often complex in nature and therefore hard to analyze with process mining**, due to their **inherent complexity and dependencies among them**.

Exemplary Statement:

- "My experience is that it is really easy to get tricked into believing that you found something interesting, but it is just due to the very complex process behavior."

question('PC07')

Do you understand the challenge?

- Yes
 No

question('PC09')

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

- Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.
 No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.
 No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

question('PC04')

Challenge: Business Process Complexity

Phase: Can potentially affect any project phase.

Description: (Real-world) **business processes are often complex in nature and therefore hard to analyze with process mining**, due to their **inherent complexity and dependencies among them**.

Exemplary Statement:

- "My experience is that it is really easy to get tricked into believing that you found something interesting, but it is just due to the very complex process behavior."

question('PC02')

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

Mitigation Approach

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

Challenge: Enablement / Training

Phase: Can potentially affect any project phase

Description: **Training and Enablement in the field of process mining is challenging.** On the one hand, there may be a **lack of available training opportunities**, or it is **not easy to find an optimal training course**, and on the other hand, **designing training courses is difficult** because knowledge from different areas is required to be successful in process mining.

Exemplary Statement:

- "Training is probably the major challenging aspect: To enable stakeholders on the methodology, but also on the operational side."

Do you understand the challenge?

Yes

No

Have you experienced the challenge yourself?

Yes, I experienced the challenge myself.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, but I can relate to it.

No, I haven't experienced the challenge, nor can I relate to it.

Challenge: Enablement / Training

Phase: Can potentially affect any project phase

Description: **Training and Enablement in the field of process mining is challenging.** On the one hand, there may be a **lack of available training opportunities**, or it is **not easy to find an optimal training course**, and on the other hand, **designing training courses is difficult** because knowledge from different areas is required to be successful in process mining.

Exemplary Statement:

- "Training is probably the major challenging aspect: To enable stakeholders on the methodology, but also on the operational side."

Please indicate your assessment.

For each of the three dimensions, please indicate how you would rate this challenge.

Uncritical Critical

Infrequent Frequent

No Blocker Project Blocker

Mitigation Approach

You indicated that you encountered the challenge already. Try to remember a situation in which the challenge occurred in one of your previous projects.

What did you do and how did you manage to overcome this challenge?

In which situation did it occur?

How did you try to overcome the challenge? Which methods / mitigation strategies / measures did you use?

Please indicate whether you could fully or partially overcome the challenge by applying the described measure(s).

0% 100%

To which extent did you manage to overcome the challenge in the project?

Do you have any additional comments / insights regarding this challenge?

Thank you for providing your detailed feedback and expertise during this survey so far!

This is the last page of the survey.

In case you have a few more minutes, we would like to hear your last thoughts about the list of challenges reported to be perceived by process mining analysts.

If you know any methods or strategies that can be used to address any of the challenges, we are happy to learn about them.

Full list of challenges:

1. **Question Formulation:** It is hard to find a question that is not too precise (might limit the analyst in the exploration of the data) and not too broad (might prevent the analyst from identifying meaningful insights).
2. **Access and Use of Process Mining Tools:** Process mining tools might be unavailable, inconvenient to use, or a governance is missing to structure the tool usage in the organization.
3. **Process Mining Suitability:** It can be difficult to select process mining as a suitable method for the task/goal/question at hand.
4. **Data Extraction:** Problems can occur during the retrieval (i.e., identification and extraction) of event data from any kind of source.
5. **Data Availability:** Event data is not always available as it might not be stored in the source system, or it is missing because process steps are conducted outside of the system.
6. **Data Access:** Permissions (legal, regulatory, organizational) or means to access the data are missing.
7. **Source System & Data Structure Knowledge:** Information and documentation of the source system and its database structure might not be available.
8. **Data Transformation:** It can be problematic to prepare a process mining compliant event log based on raw event data.
9. **Data Quality:** It can be problematic to deal with data of low quality either in the final event log or already in the raw data.
10. **Data Validation:** It can be difficult to check the data accuracy or the suitability of the available data to be analyzed with the help of process mining.
11. **Tool Knowledge:** The analyst is not familiar with the tool, lacks knowledge on how to use specific functions of the tool or hasn't used the tool in a while.
12. **Event Log & Data Model Understanding:** Data models or event logs can come in different formats and with different levels of complexity and elements.

13. **Process Mining Techniques:** Process mining tools are missing (or insufficiently support) certain process mining functionalities.
14. **Access to Additional Information:** Permissions to access the process documentations or the option to collaborate with knowledgeable stakeholders (e.g., process owner) are missing, or such information regarding the specific process simply do not exist.
15. **Process Visualization:** The interpretation of the visualization of a process in form of a directly-follows-graph (DFG) (as used in many process mining tools) is challenging as they are not able to deal with concurrency and should be cautiously read when filtered.
16. **Analysis Experience:** It can be problematic to conduct an analysis if the analyst doesn't have a lot of experience but at the same time, gaining the experience and finding project partners with the required experience and skillset is challenging.
17. **Analysis Focus:** It can be problematic to maintain the big picture of the analysis despite the available details.
18. **Conclusions & Question Answering:** It is not trivial to draw conclusions based on the results of the process discovery.
19. **Recommendations & Next steps:** Formulating a concrete recommendation or deriving concrete next steps to foster the process improvement is not always straightforward based on the analysis insights.
20. **Process Domain Understanding:** The analysts might not be familiar with the domain & domain-specific terminology that is used in the event and attribute descriptions.
21. **Collaboration with Stakeholders:** There can be misunderstandings due to mismatching expectations, different process perspectives and different backgrounds of the stakeholders and the analysts.
22. **Business Process Complexity:** Business processes are oftentimes complex in nature and therefore hard to analyze with process mining, due to their inherent complexity and dependencies among them.
23. **Enablement / Training:** On the one hand, there may be a lack of available training opportunities, or it is not easy to find an optimal training course, and on the other hand, designing training courses is difficult because knowledge from different areas is required to be successful in process mining.

In case you are interested in the academic paper, in which these challenges are presented in more detail, you can find it by searching for "Process Mining Challenges Perceived by Analysts: An interview study" (Link was removed due to practical reasons, but feel free to reach out to me to receive it via e-mail).

9. Do you want to add anything else?

Thank you for considering participating in this survey! Unfortunately, we require participants who have practical experience in the conduct of process mining projects.

However, if you like to stay in touch and receive the results of this study, please leave your mail address on the next page.

If you have any further questions or comments, please contact: lisa.zimmermann@unisg.ch

10. If you would like to receive the results of this study and stay in touch regarding further information or publications of the ProMISE project, please leave your e-mail address.

- I am interested in the results of the study.
- I am interested to stay in touch & receive further information regarding the ProMISE Project.

Thank you for completing this questionnaire!

We would like to thank you very much for helping us.

Your answers were transmitted, you may close the browser window or tab now.